

VARIATION OF RELATIVE VISCOSITY WITH TEMPERATURE.
ORGANIC SOLUTES IN NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS

By A. C. CHATTERJI AND A. N. BOSE

The variation of relative viscosity with temperature has been studied. In most of the systems studied here the value of $\frac{\delta}{\delta t} \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_o} \right)$ is negative but for the systems of butyl alcohol-phthalic acid, butyl alcohol-succinic acid, and propyl alcohol-succinic acid the value of $\frac{\delta}{\delta t} \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_o} \right)$ is almost zero at lower concentrations. This may be due to the fact that the molecules of butyl alcohol and propyl alcohol are less associated than the molecules of methyl alcohol.

In a previous communication (Chatterji and Bose, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 91) the variation of relative viscosity with temperature has been studied. In this paper the same work has been extended to other systems of organic solutes in non-aqueous solvents

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The method employed is the same as in the previous paper. Results calculated from the viscosity data, thus obtained, are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Solute.	Conc. (g./100 g.)	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.	55°.
Solvent=Methyl alcohol.								
Benzoic acid	68.0	2.373	2.300	2.253	2.221	2.201	—	—
	83.0	—	2.614	2.564	2.512	2.448	—	—
Salicylic acid	65.0	—	—	2.153	2.131	2.077	2.040	—
	75.0	—	—	2.292	2.269	2.221	2.190	—
Phthalic acid	33.0	—	—	2.228	2.208	2.170	2.116	—
	24.6	—	—	1.879	1.850	1.806	1.783	—
Cinnamic acid	37.5	—	—	1.900	1.852	1.827	1.798	—
	50.3	—	—	2.242	2.196	2.132	2.208	—
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	110.0	—	—	3.863	3.782	3.658	3.528	—
	156.0	—	—	5.031	5.260	5.421	5.690	—
Succinic acid	19.6	—	—	1.653	1.641	1.624	1.604	—
	27.8	—	—	1.960	1.943	1.901	1.887	—

TABLE I (contd.)

Solute.	Conc. (g./100 g.)	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.	55°.
Solvent = Propyl alcohol.								
Benzoic acid	68.2	—	—	—	1.686	1.680	1.670	1.650
	42.2	—	—	1.456	1.448	1.438	1.428	1.411
Salicylic acid	54.0	—	—	—	1.545	1.527	1.525	1.507
	43.0	—	—	1.435	1.432	1.426	1.417	1.403
Phthalic acid	10.6	—	—	1.359	1.344	1.331	1.316	1.299
	5.6	—	—	1.173	1.167	1.160	1.151	1.138
Cinnamic acid	30.3	—	—	1.555	1.536	1.504	1.490	1.456
	18.2	—	—	1.316	1.308	1.296	1.285	1.260
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	108.4	—	—	—	—	3.146	3.057	2.945
	78.8	—	—	—	—	2.393	2.330	2.263
Succinic acid	6.1	—	—	1.118	1.118	1.118	1.1173	1.1170
	9.8	—	—	—	1.309	1.302	1.294	1.283
Solvent = Butyl alcohol.								
Salicylic acid	44.5	—	—	1.373	1.364	1.355	1.366	1.359
	30.3	—	—	1.220	1.229	1.229	1.230	1.220
Phthalic acid	4.9	—	—	1.142	1.141	1.136	1.136	1.135
	7.3	—	—	—	1.224	1.213	1.213	1.207
Cinnamic acid	21.2	—	—	—	1.315	1.304	1.300	1.288
	15.7	—	—	1.235	1.228	1.214	1.213	1.207
Succinic acid	2.7	—	—	1.077	1.071	1.071	1.070	1.069
	7.8	—	—	—	—	1.222	1.223	1.214

DISCUSSION

It has been suggested in the previous paper that if the solvent consists of associated molecules and the solute forms solvates with the solvent molecules, the value of $\delta/\delta t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ should be either positive or negative, depending upon which of the two factors, viz. depolymerisation of the solvent molecules or breaking up of the solvate complexes predominates. From the results given in Table I it is observed that for almost all the systems studied here, the value of $\delta/\delta t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ is negative except for the systems of butyl alcohol—phthalic acid, butyl alcohol—succinic acid and propyl alcohol—succinic acid the value of $\delta/\delta t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ is almost zero at lower concentrations.

As in this paper highly concentrated solutions have been taken, the effect of depolymerisation of the solvent molecule is negligible as compared to the breaking up of the solvate complexes, and therefore the value of $\delta/\delta t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ for these systems are negative.

If we examine the systems studied here, we find that for the systems where the solvent has got low value for dipole moment *i.e.* where the association of the solvent molecule is less, the negative value of $\delta/\delta t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ is less than the solvents where the association of the solvent molecule is more marked. In case of the systems of methyl alcohol, the negative value for $\delta/\delta t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ is much more than the systems for propyl alcohol which in turn is more than the systems of butyl alcohol. The dipole moment of butyl alcohol is greater than that of propyl alcohol which again is greater than that of methyl alcohol.

For the systems of butyl alcohol the value of $\delta/\delta t(\eta_s/\eta_0)$ is zero in some cases, it is just possible that for the systems of higher alcohols the value may be also zero.

One of us (A. N. B.) is thankful to the U.P. Government for the grant of a research fellowship.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received August 3, 1948.